

EU-DREAM

Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets

D8.1 Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CEN	European Committee for Standardization (Comité Européen de Normalisation)
CMS	Content Management System
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DT	Digital Twin
EU	European Union
GBC	Green Building Council
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LL	Living Lab
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OA	Open Access
PM	Person Month
PR	Press Release
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TG	Target Group
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UNE	Asociación Española de Normalización (Spanish Association for Standardization)
WP	Work Package

CONSORTIUM

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2 (Partner)	Cleanwatts Digital SA	CWD	PT
3 (Partner)	EPRI Europe DAC	EEU	IE
4 (Partner)	SSE Airtricity LTD	SSEA	IE
5 (Partner)	DCSix Technologies Limited	DCS	IE
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EU-DREAM project (Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets) is a 42-month Horizon Europe project focused on improving consumer interaction with the energy market. It aims to simplify complex energy management processes and enhance customer awareness, trust, and confidence through the introduction of an Artificial Intelligence (AI) -based assistant and a Natural Language Processing (NLP) intermediary.

The project is divided into 9 Work Packages (WP), with WP8 focusing on Communication, Exploitation, and Dissemination activities during and beyond the project's lifetime. WP8 aims to generate project awareness and visibility, maximizing the impact of the solutions developed. WP8 comprises four tasks:

- Task 8.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan
- Task 8.2: Exploitation Plan
- Task 8.3: Regulatory, Policy, and Market Recommendations
- Task 8.4: Networking, Outreach, and Stakeholder Engagement

This is a transversal WP, led by EEU, where all project partners participate (except IME), with a total of 45 Person/Month (PM's).

This deliverable, D8.1 Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan, outlines strategies and actions for effectively conveying information to target audiences and ensuring widespread distribution of the project messages and findings. This report focuses on messaging, channels, timing, and the intended impact to achieve specific objectives. The deliverable is divided into three main chapters: Communication and Dissemination Plan; Communication Tools and Actions and Communication Campaigns. An update of this deliverable will be provided at M14 (August 2025) and M28 (October 2026).

The EU-DREAM project is expected to significantly improve consumer interaction with the energy market, leading to increased energy efficiency and more informed, empowered energy consumers.

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Introduction

The EU-DREAM project is a 42-month Horizon Europe initiative designed to enhance consumer interaction with the energy market. This project aims to simplify complex energy management processes and foster customer awareness, trust, and confidence through innovative technologies, including an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based assistant and a Natural Language Processing (NLP) intermediary. By enabling more informed and active participation in energy transitions and markets, EU-DREAM addresses critical challenges in the energy sector.

WP8 aims at to address all the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities of EU-DREAM, following the below objectives:

- Ensure maximum project visibility and impact by efficiently communicating project innovations;
- Promote synergies with the energy industry, such as system operators, retailers and producers, as well as with the scientific community, including organizations active in related projects to combine efforts and accelerate dissemination;
- Identify the best exploitation of the project results during and after the project;
- Organise a constant dialogue with the relevant stakeholders.

As part of WP8, this deliverable, D8.1 Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan, is a fundamental piece of addressing the WP objectives, serving as a foundational document for the project's communication and dissemination efforts. Its primary purpose is to outline the strategies and actions necessary for effectively conveying information to target audiences and ensuring the widespread dissemination of project results. By establishing a clear and comprehensive communication framework, this deliverable aims to support the project's objectives of enhancing consumer engagement and facilitating the uptake of digital energy services.

The scope of D8.1 includes a detailed plan for dissemination and communication activities throughout the project's lifecycle and beyond. It covers the identification of target audiences, key messages, communication channels, and tools to be utilised. Additionally, it outlines the timing and frequency of communication efforts to ensure maximum impact.

This deliverable is divided into three main chapters:

1. Communication and Dissemination Plan: This chapter outlines the overarching strategy, including target audiences, key messages, and planned activities.
2. Communication Tools and Actions: This chapter details the specific tools and actions to be employed, such as digital platforms, events, publications, and other outreach activities to be used to implement the strategy.
3. Communication Campaigns: This chapter outlines the objectives and timeline for specific communication activities, which are adjusted to the project timeline and milestones. The aim is to clearly define the goals of each campaign and establish a structured timeframe to ensure effective and timely execution and impact. It also includes a monitoring strategy that will be implemented continuously to ensure that the

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are achieved. If the KPIs are not met, the strategy will allow for planning and adjustments to address any deviations.

Updates to this deliverable will be provided at M14 and M28 to ensure that the dissemination and communication efforts remain aligned with the project's progress and evolving needs.

Communication and Dissemination Plan

Communication refers to the strategic promotion of the project brand, activities and results to a broad audience to enhance visibility, engagement, and understanding of the project's impact and relevance. In contrast, Dissemination involves the targeted distribution of project results to specific stakeholders and communities to ensure the uptake and application of the knowledge generated during the project.

In essence, while communication focuses on the strategic promotion and engagement of stakeholders, dissemination ensures that the knowledge and outcomes generated by the project reach and benefit targeted audiences, thereby maximizing the project's overall impact and sustainability. Both communication and dissemination efforts are aligned with the overall project objectives and goals and both can be used to amplify the impact of project outcomes, contributing to the long-term sustainability of project impacts.

The key objectives of the dissemination and communication plan are:

- A. To raise awareness about the EU-DREAM project and its goals among all target audience
- B. To disseminate project results and findings to relevant audiences in a timely and effective manner.
- C. To engage stakeholders and foster collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- D. Raise awareness about the importance of consumer-centric approaches for the *Digitalisation of the Energy System*;
- E. Promote an understanding of the digital tools and technologies that are being developed, thus helping improving energy literacy;
- F. To build trust and confidence in the digital energy services facilitated by AI and NLP technologies.
- G. Ensure broad visibility of the project;
- H. Contribute to the creation of synergies between Horizon EU-supported actions.

Within the EU-DREAM project, Communication covers all actions to spread information on EU-DREAM's results beyond the consortium, maximising contributions to the European energy industry and attracting key stakeholders to benefit from EU-DREAM's innovative solutions.

Communication activities will spread information about EU-DREAM's results using various channels (online, offline, networks) to ensure maximum visibility of the project towards all Target Groups (TGs). Key communication elements are the project logo and the templates, infographics, posters and flyers, project website, social media activities (Twitter and LinkedIn), newsletter, technology brochure, promotional videos, press releases, joint events, workshops and networking, training workshops and webinars.

Dissemination towards TGs aims to maximize the visibility of the outcomes. This will be done via direct visitations to LLs, a best practices and recommendations manual for industry and policy-makers, contributions to standards, technical committees and regulations, a network of collaborations with joint meetings and clustering with other EU consortia, workshops and webinars, publications in peer-reviewed Open Access (OA) scientific journals, presentations in

scientific conferences, participation in EU and industry events, fairs and exhibitions, summer schools, master classes and seminars, and IEEE SG Initiative contributions.

The main principle of the Dissemination activities in EU-DREAM is to make use of the innovative results and main achievements to create value within the TG, communities and initiatives of the EU.

Target Audience

Within the EU-DREAM project, we identified 7 Target Groups (TG1-TG7) from potential stakeholders, as detailed below:

- TG1 Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia.
- TG2 Energy Industry, including
 - a) TG2.1: Energy Producers;
 - b) TG2.2: Grid Operators (DSOs and TSOs);
 - c) TG2.3: Energy Communities;
 - d) TG2.4: Energy Retailers and Aggregators;
 - e) TG2.5: Energy Service Companies (e.g., ESCOs) and Energy Efficiency Consultants;
 - f) TG2.6: Other Energy Companies.
- TG3 Non-profit Organisations, including
 - a) TG3.1: System Operators Associations (e.g., E.DSO);
 - b) TG3.2: Consumer Organisations (e.g., ECC-Network);
 - c) TG3.3: Energy Generators' Associations;
 - d) TG3.4: Environmental Organisations;
 - e) TG3.5: Other Non-Profit.
- TG4 Technology Providers, including Companies developing/providing Software (SW) platforms, Hardware (HW) devices, Communication networks, Data analytics tools, Cybersecurity solutions, and IoT devices.
- TG5 General Public and Civil Society, including Individual Energy Consumers, Prosumers and Customers.
- TG6 Policy Makers, Regulators and Public Authorities at European, National and Regional levels, including Governments, Governmental Agencies and Parliaments.
- TG7 Standardisation Bodies, including IEC, IEEE, ISO, UNE, CEN and GBC.

These TGs will further up-take EU-DREAM results, thus benefiting from the results of the project.

EU-DREAM will promote awareness creation and knowledge building within the TGs. The dissemination approach and strategies will be tailored to each partner's expertise.

Key Messages

While keeping our target audience clear is fundamental to know who we want to communicate the project to. Having tailored messages is crucial as it ensures that communication efforts are tailored to address their interests, needs, and expectations. This approach enhances engagement, fosters collaboration, and maximizes the impact of the project across diverse stakeholder communities.

The project main message lies within its motto: Bridging the digital divide in energy, which underscores various dimensions of the EU-DREAM project. It will be used largely across several communication materials, channels and occasions to enhance the various dimensions of the project:

- Digital Inclusion and Accessibility
- Empowerment of communities and individual through Technology – customer centric approach
- Enhancing Efficiency and Sustainability of the energy management/system, facilitating the energy transition
- Fostering innovation within the energy sector.

Nonetheless, specific oriented tailored messages will be used on times depending on the target group, as summarised in Table 1 Target Groups and Tailored Key Messages.

Table 1 Target Groups and Tailored Key Messages

TG	Key Messages
TG1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight the project's scientific contributions, innovative methodologies, and potential for advancing knowledge in energy management and AI/NLP technologies. • Emphasize opportunities for collaboration, joint research, and academic publications arising from project outcomes.
TG2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the project's outcomes and its potential to optimize energy production and grid management. • Showcase how the project aligns with industry trends towards sustainability and decarbonization. • Highlight potential cost savings and operational efficiencies for grid operators. • Communicate the benefits of community-based energy management and the empowerment of local stakeholders through AI-driven solutions. • Highlight new business models opportunities. • Highlight the project's contributions to energy efficiency, cost reduction, and sustainable practices.
TG3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailor messages to each subgroup focusing on project impacts relevant to their missions and objectives. • Focus on promoting digital and energy literacy
TG4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on how the project advance on technological innovation, e.g. software platforms, hardware devices, communication networks, digital tools, AI tools and NLP advancements. • Digital Twin (DT) with AI-NLP can optimise data-driven services to enhance energy literacy, benefiting from data sharing and increased interoperability;

- TG5**

 - How the project improves energy affordability, reliability, and sustainability for households and communities.
 - Energy literacy messages.
 - Consumers can be empowered with user-friendly and simplified digital platforms, facilitating the investment in energy transition
- TG6**

 - Highlight regulatory implications, policy recommendations, and potential for scaling up successful pilot projects.
- TG7**

 - Highlight the project's contributions to advancing standards in energy management, AI/NLP technologies, cybersecurity, etc.

Communication Tools and Actions

The marketing communication tools encompass a variety of strategies aimed at effectively engaging with an audience. As such, our project will utilize four key tools: advertising, digital marketing, public relations, and direct marketing. Each tool involves specific actions tailored to meet distinct objectives and audience targets, as outlined in Table 2 Communication tools, actions alignment with objectives and target groups, contributing significantly to our communication and dissemination initiatives.

Table 2 Communication tools, actions alignment with objectives and target groups

Communication Tool	Action	Objective	TGs
Advertising	Logo, brochure, poster, roll-up	A,C,G, E	All
	Videos	A, C, G, E	All
Digital Marketing	Website	All	All
	Social Media	All	TG1, TG2, TG4, TG6, TG7
Direct Marketing	Newsletter	B,C,D,E,F,H	TG1, TG2, TG4, TG6, TG7
	Press release	A,G, E	TG3, TG5
Public relations	Events	All	TG1, TG2, TG4, TG6, TG7

Advertising

Project Visual Brand Identity

The visual identity plays a crucial role in ensuring consistent visuals that unify the brand's messaging, thereby enhancing communication coherence and boosting recognition across channels. It includes an identity manual detailing the project logo, colour schemes, variations, and fonts.

Various communication materials have been crafted based on this visual identity to promote the project, detailed individually in the following sub-chapters, together with associated templates for presentations and marketing collateral. All materials are documented in Appendix 1 Project Visual Brand Identity

Logo

The central element of the logo is the 'cloud', symbolizing digital services, with embedded concepts of consumer interaction and artificial intelligence, as shown in Figure 1 Project Logo. Blue was chosen as the primary colour to signify digital services, while 'coloured dots' represent a connected community, highlighting other key themes of the project.

The font selected is Aгенor Neue Regular, characterized by a linear and clear style, complemented by a distinctive curvilinear stroke that harmonizes with the logo design. Additionally, Open Sans is used for supplementary text to maintain consistency and readability.

Figure 1 Project Logo

As part of the brand development, a library of brand icons and elements was created (Figure 2 Library of brand icons) to delineate the project's scope and areas of focus, as illustrated in graphics available in the Appendix 2 Project Scope Infographics

Figure 2 Library of brand icons

Communication material: poster, roll-up banner, flyer and leaflet

A roll up banner, poster, leaflet and flyer have been designed for distribution at events to help partners communicate the project's main messages, including its goals, expected results,

impacts, and solutions. Additionally, a project summary overview has also been prepared. These materials are in the

Appendix 3 Project Roll-up banner, poster, leaflet and flyer

. A digital version will be available on the project website and the materials will be showcased and distributed in industry events. See Appendix 4 Project Summary Overview

Tailored materials specific to the Living Labs will be crucial to keeping participants informed about the project and expected outcomes. A detailed leaflet will be designed and translated into the local languages of the countries where the Living Labs are located. Additionally, a comprehensive brochure containing all Living Labs information will be produced.

Finally, a brochure gathering key technology information about the technologies developed will be made available.

Video

A kick-off video highlighting the main motto of the project and its benefit, with real images from the meeting held in Porto was shared on project social media to raise awareness for the project. More simply and short-form videos with oriented messages are being crafted during the first six months of the project to provide visibility and awareness (as part of the Communication Campaign 1, introduced later in this report).

A motion graphics video is being created to effectively communicate the project's concept in a visually engaging and easily understandable manner to a wider audience. The video will introduce the project's context, identify the challenges it aims to address, present the solutions being developed and tested, and discuss the expected impacts. It will be distributed across the project's primary communication channels: website, social media platforms, and newsletters.

The video is expected to be live in October 2024.

At least three more videos will be produced during the project, aiming at creating awareness for the Living labs and the projects' results.

Digital Marketing

Website

A dedicated website using the domain www.eu-dream.eu is being developed to communicate the project's activities and disseminate its outcomes. The project website offers visitors:

- Contextual information about the project, its challenges, milestones, and desired outcomes.
- Information about each living lab
- Access to useful resources, such as deliverables, scientific papers and others, for more information on EU-DREAM developments and results.
- Updates on the latest news and project-related events.
- Contact details for further inquiries.

The website structure is illustrated in Figure 3 Website and is divided in the following main pages:

1. Homepage – outlines project tagline, main figures, and latest updates.
2. About the project: context, objectives, benefits, and impact.
3. Living labs – with information on goals, specifics, and expected outcomes. This page will have a leaflet with information in the LL country language.
4. Resources – all technical outcomes of the project, including deliverables, reports, scientific publications, technical presentations and factsheets, roadmaps and policy recommendations.
5. Partners – information about the partners.
6. Communication – will feature news, events, communication materials and project newsletters.
7. Contacts - has a form that can be used to send message to the project coordinator and the social media links. And as for to subscribe newsletter.

Figure 3 Website architecture.

The website features its own Content Management System (CMS) and integrates with the project's social media profiles. It will include a subscription form for visitors to join the project newsletter and provides contact details for reaching out to the project coordinator and communications leader via email.

Website traffic and downloads will be tracked using the Matomo Analytics tool, an open-source platform endorsed by the European Commission. It offers anonymized yet insightful data on user behaviour, ensuring compliance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The project targets achieving five thousand visits annually.

The site is expected to be live in October 2024.

Social Media

The project has selected Twitter (Twitter: EU-DREAM, n.d.) and LinkedIn (LinkedIn: EU-DREAM, n.d.) as its primary social media platforms. LinkedIn will be instrumental in informing and engaging with research, academia, technology providers and the energy industry, while Twitter will help connect the project with policy and standardization bodies and non-profits. Social

media, being a free and accessible tool with a diverse audience, will enable the project to reach the public sphere, thereby raising awareness among a broader audience that includes all key target groups.

Social media activities will be conducted on a weekly basis and will comply with the project visual identity in order to maintain consistency, which is crucial for driving reach and engagement.

The content shared will follow the strategy and timeframe highlighted for each communication campaign described in the next chapter of this deliverable. Therefore, at this stage, the content shared on social media will cover the project's context, objectives, benefits, consortium and living labs, to raise awareness and provide essential information.

The impact of these efforts will be tracked using the analytics tools provided by Twitter and LinkedIn. Growth in followers and impressions will serve as indicators of the project's reach and influence, while engagement will measure the effectiveness of the content in fostering active participation. The goal is to achieve at least three hundred impressions and ten engagements per post.

Figure 4 EU-DREAM LinkedIn and Twitter shows screenshots of the project's pages on LinkedIn and Twitter.

Figure 4 EU-DREAM LinkedIn and Twitter

Public Relations

Press releases

Media outlets serve as crucial and credible intermediaries to engage with a wider audience.

Consequently, the project aims to distribute a minimum of 8 press releases (PRs), with a total of 25 media insertions. The first release was issued in Month 1 to announce the project's commencement, documented in the Appendix 5 Press Releases sent in Ireland, Portugal, Greece, Belgium and Italy

. Partners were tasked with translating, adapting to local specificities and disseminating it within their networks across the nine countries involved in the project.

Until the submission date of this deliverable, the press release was translated into Portuguese, Greek, French, Dutch and Italian, and sent to journalists across five countries (Ireland, Portugal, Belgium, Italy, and Greece), as well as to wider European outlets. Details of the press release insertions on the media are summarized in Table 3 Press Release insertions on the Media.

Table 3 Press Release insertions on the Media

Country	Media Outlet	Title & Link
Ireland	Irish Tech News	New European Project Aims to Increase Consumers' Involvement in the Energy Market by Using AI
	Silicon Republic	EU project wants consumers to engage with energy using AI
	Bakenas	New European Project Aims to Increase Consumers' Involvement in the Energy Market by Using AI
Portugal	Observador	Universidade do Porto lidera projeto para melhorar interação de consumidores no mercado de energia
	Noticias ao Minuto	U.Porto lidera projeto para melhorar interação com mercado de energia
	Scooper News	U.Porto lidera projeto para melhorar interação com mercado de energia
Greece	Energy Press	Νέο ευρωπαϊκό έργο για την αύξηση της συμμετοχής των καταναλωτών στην αγορά ενέργειας με τη χρήση τεχνητής νοημοσύνης
Belgium	Entrepreneur	https://aannemer.pmg.be/fr/dossier/EESbe2431S03_00/le-projet-europeen-dream-vise-a-impliquer-dav
	Projecto	https://projecto.pmg.be/nl/dossier/EESbe2431S03_00/eu-dream-project-wil-via-ai-consumenten-meer
	Sanilec	https://sanilec.pmg.be/fr/dossier/EESbe2431S03_00/le-projet-europeen-dream-vise-a-impliquer-dav
	Salinec	https://sanilec.pmg.be/nl/dossier/EESbe2431S03_00/eu-dream-project-wil-via-ai-consumenten-meer

In an effort to amplify the project reach, some partners have also published information on other online channels, as shown in Table 4 Other online channels with project information.

Table 4 Other online channels with project information

Channel	Link
UPorto News Portal	https://noticias.up.pt/2024/07/16/feup-lidera-projeto-de-45-milhoes-de-euros-para-envolver-consumidores-no-mercado-de-energia/
EEU website	https://europe.epri.com/project/eu-dream
ARISE website	https://arise-la.pt/eu-dream-kick-off-meeting/
LINKS website	https://linksfoundation.com/en/progetti/eu-dream-2/
AAL website	https://vbn.aau.dk/en/projects/effective-uptake-of-digital-services-to-repower-european-consumer
VITO website	https://vito.be/en/news/eu-dream-project-aims-increase-consumers%E2%80%99-involvement-energy-market-using-ai

ENSIEL

<https://consorzioensiel.it/progetti-di-ricerca/progetti-europei/eu-dream-effective-uptake-of-digital-services-to-repower-european-consumers-and-communities-as-active-participants-in-energy-transition-and-markets/>

Events

Events provide a vital platform to engage with the project audience, exchange knowledge, and share findings. We will actively promote presentations at top scientific conferences and participation in EU and industry events, fairs, and exhibitions. Our strategy includes attending events organized by experts, researchers, clients, and industry professionals, where project partners will present their work and vision. We aim to target various stakeholder groups, including technical and managerial staff, as well as the general public and consumers, to inform them about the benefits, best practices, and specific adaptations of our project.

To date, we have identified the following key events:

- EU Innovation Days
- Enlit Europe
- EUSEW
- Innogrid
- CIRED
- IEEE T&D

Workshops will be essential for maximizing the adoption of project solutions, with a priority on Living Labs activities. These workshops, conducted in collaboration with Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) experts, aim to enhance user adoption and develop solutions that promote energy literacy.

Other events such as webinars will be targeting various stakeholder groups to inform them about benefits, best practices and specific adaptations.

We will also organise summer schools, master classes and seminars to facilitate knowledge exchange and uptake of results with academia and research communities.

Direct Marketing

Newsletter

The newsletter will serve as the primary direct marketing tool for engaging with project stakeholders, including a wider audience. It adheres to a structured template layout, featuring:

- Cover story: Highlighting a significant milestone, outcome, or news piece with accompanying visuals (photo, infographic, or video).
- News & events: Recap of past activities and previews of upcoming events.
- Resources: Links to useful materials and resources related to the project.
- Scientific Publications: Updates on publications and research outputs.
- Public deliverables & Other reports: Access to project deliverables and additional reports.

- Communication materials: Information on promotional materials developed for the project.
- Contacts, acknowledgments, and unsubscribe option.

All project partners are encouraged to contribute to the newsletter. The management and distribution of the newsletter are facilitated through the digital marketing platform which will be selected at a later stage.

The newsletter will be distributed to all subscribers biannually. Subscriptions to the project newsletter can be completed through the footer of the project website.

The inaugural project newsletter will be sent in December 2024.

Clustering activities and other initiatives

Collaborative meetings and clustering with other EU consortia under the REPowerEU initiative and various European workgroups will be planned to share knowledge, resources, and best practices, thereby enhancing the overall impact of the projected and promoting innovation.

Among these, EU-DREAM will be involved in BRIDGE, an initiative directly supported by the European Commission that unites all Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects in the energy sector. EU-DREAM will be involved in four working groups: Data Management, Business Models, Regulation, and Consumer and Citizen Engagement.

By participating in BRIDGE, EU-DREAM can collaborate with similar projects to understand their activities and identify synergies. Engaging with other projects on topics relevant to EU-DREAM allows us to gather valuable insights that we might not have the resources to explore independently.

Scientific publications

EU-DREAM is committed to fully supporting open science practices, The project will actively pursue Open Access (OA) publishing, using a dedicated budget for Gold OA and leveraging transformative agreements for Green OA. The OA publications will be made available on the project website. The goal is to publish at least 20 OA journal articles, present at 20 top scientific conferences, and participate in EU and industry events, fairs, and exhibitions.

The targeted journals include IEEE TII, IEEE IoTJ, IEEE TNNLS, IEEE TCC, IEEE TSG, IEEE TSTE, APEN, IEEE TPWRS, ENERGY, SEGAN, IJEPES, EPSR, IEEE TIE and IEEE TIA.

The presentations in scientific conferences include PSCC, IEEE PowerTech, SEST, IEEE PES GM, IEEE IECON, IEEE MELECON, IEEE EUROCON, UPEC, IEEE INDIN, IEEE IC, IEEE IAS, ISGT, EEM, CCTA and HICSS.

Acknowledgment and disclaimer for publications

The authors of publications in EU-DREAM are committed to indicate the following acknowledgment and disclaimer in the publications referring to the project:

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Communication Campaigns

EU-DREAM work plan proposes a series of logical and interrelated 9 WPs over 42 months that will enable the project to meet its objectives. Each WP is characterised by well-defined objectives and measurable outcomes. The path to scalability and replicability in EU-DREAM will be based on user-driven interaction and evaluation towards validation and assessment after the successful integration and deployment of platforms and tools. EU-DREAM has 3 well-balanced Phases:

- Phase 1 (M1-M18)– Data-driven cross-sector services, solutions, products (WP1); DT, AI-based assistant tool and NLP-based intermediary (WP2); Data sharing, security, interoperability (WP3).
- Phase 2 (M13-M36)– Digital tools, platforms and energy data visualisation (WP4); Energy and flexibility markets (WP5); Digital empowerment, energy literacy and social innovation tools (WP6).
- Phase 3 (M10-M42)– Demonstration and validation with 6 LLs in 6 EU countries, including scalability/replicability, go-to-market strategy, Business Plan, intertwining SSH contributions with LLs (WP7).

Developing targeted communication campaigns aligned with each phase of the EU-DREAM project would be highly beneficial for maximizing impact and achieving project objectives. So we suggest the following five communication campaigns.

Campaign 1: Initial Awareness (M1-M6)

Objectives:

- Introduce EU-DREAM project to key stakeholders and the general public.
- Create awareness about the project's goals, significance, and expected outcomes.
- Establish a foundation for ongoing engagement and support throughout the project.

Key Activities:

- Website and Social Media Launch: Develop a project website and social media profiles to share updates, resources, and engage with stakeholders.
- Press Releases and Media Outreach: Distribute press releases and engage with media outlets to generate coverage and interest in the project.
- Videos and other communication materials launch.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Reach out to target groups (scientific communities, industry, policymakers) through targeted emails, newsletters, and direct communications.

Target Groups:

All

Timeline:

Months 1-6

Campaign 2: Technology Showcase and Development (M7-M18)

Objectives

- Highlight the development of AI-based tools, NLP intermediaries, and data interoperability solutions.
- Showcase technological advancements.
- Position EU-DREAM as a leader in integrating digital technologies into the energy sector.

Key Activities:

- Technology Demonstrations: Conduct demonstrations of AI tools, NLP solutions, and data interoperability platforms at industry conferences, workshops, or webinars.
- Cooperation with BRIDGE and other EU-funded projects/initiatives.

Target Groups

- TG1 Scientific Communities, R&D and Academia
- TG2 Energy Industry
- TG4 Technology Providers
- TG7 Standardisation Bodies

Timeline:

Months 7-18

Campaign 3: Digital Tools and Empowerment (M13-M36)

Objectives:

- Communicate advancements in digital platforms, energy data visualization, and empowerment tools.
- Highlight progress in developing digital tools for energy literacy, social innovation, and community engagement.
- Prepare stakeholders for upcoming pilot deployments and market integration.

Key Activities:

- Tool and Platform Updates: Share updates on digital platforms, data visualization tools, and advancements in energy management technologies.
- Empowerment Initiatives: Launch campaigns focused on energy literacy, social innovation, and community engagement tools.
- Pre-Pilot Engagement: Prepare stakeholders (including potential pilot participants) for upcoming pilot deployments through technical fact sheets on tools and results, LLs brochures, LL visits, targeted workshops, training sessions, and informational webinars.

Target Groups

- TG4 Technology Providers
- TG2 Energy Industry, especially, TG2.3: Energy Communities;
- TG3 Non-profit Organisation
- TG5 General Public and Civil Society, including Individual Energy Consumers, Prosumers and Customers, and especially the LL participants

Timeline:

- Months M13-M36

Campaign 4: Market Integration and Pilot Results (M25-M36)

Objectives:

- Communicate advancements in digital platforms and their integration into energy and flexibility markets.
- Highlight pilot project progress, outcomes, and lessons learned.
- Engage stakeholders in industry adoption and market transformation.

Key Activities:

- Market Integration Updates: Share updates on digital platform integrations with energy and flexibility markets through newsletters, webinars, and industry publications.
- Pilot Deployment Highlights: Highlight pilot projects' progress, outcomes, and lessons learned through case studies, webinars, and targeted presentations.
- Industry Workshops and Training: Organize workshops and training sessions to educate industry stakeholders on adopting and utilizing project innovations.

Target Groups

- All

Timeline:

- Months 31-36

Campaign 5: Final Results and Outcomes (M37-M42)

Objectives:

- Communicate the final results, outcomes, and achievements of the EU-DREAM project.
- Highlight the impact and benefits of project innovations on stakeholders and the energy sector.
- Facilitate the uptake and utilization of project results by stakeholders.

Key Activities:

- **Results Dissemination:** Publish comprehensive reports, case studies, and white papers summarizing the project's findings, innovations, and outcomes. Make these available through the project website, social media channels, and targeted distribution to stakeholders.
- **Showcase Events:** Organize a final showcase event, conference, or webinar to present key findings, success stories, and demonstrations of project innovations. Invite stakeholders, policymakers, industry representatives, and the general public.
- **Media Outreach:** Conduct targeted media outreach to generate coverage and interest in the project's final outcomes and impact. Prepare press releases and engage with relevant media outlets to ensure broad dissemination.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Engage with key stakeholders through personalized communications, workshops, and presentations to ensure they understand and are equipped to implement project results.
- **Legacy and Sustainability Planning:** Develop strategies and recommendations for sustaining project outcomes beyond the project duration. This includes business plans, scalability assessments, and policy recommendations based on project learnings.

Target Groups

All

Timeline:

- Months 37-42

A summary of the 5 campaigns is shown in Figure 5 Summary of the Communication Campaigns.

Figure 5 Summary of the Communication Campaigns

This adjusted approach ensures that communication efforts are strategically phased to maximize impact and engagement throughout the EU-DREAM project. Each campaign is aligned with key project milestones and deliverables, ensuring that stakeholders are informed and engaged at critical stages of technological development, pilot testing, and market integration. The campaigns will be updated in subsequent deliverables.

Monitoring and Impact Strategy

The monitoring and evaluation of C&D KPIs will be conducted continuously. Matomo Analytics will be used to track website performance, while social media KPIs will be monitored through their built-in analytics tools. Video analytics will be derived from social media platforms. The chosen newsletter platform will also provide detailed analytics. A comprehensive communication and dissemination log will be maintained to record all activities conducted by consortium partners.

Continuous monitoring will enable us to adjust strategies and implement corrective measures when actions do not meet expectations.

Table 5 C&D KPIs and Target Value outlines the KPIs for each communication and dissemination action and the results achieved up to M3.

Table 5 C&D KPIs and Target Value

Communication & Dissemination actions	KPI and Target Value	M3 update
<i>Project Visual Identity: This includes developing a professional-quality project logo together with associated templates for all presentation and marketing collaterals and a service/project motto.</i>	100% of communication materials will be compliant with the project's visual identity and branding.	All materials designed so far are compliant with visual identity
<i>Communication Materials: Development of infographics, posters/rollups and flyers/leaflets/postcards</i>	No. of distributed communication material: > 500 (copies distributed, including printing and download).	Infographic, poster, roll up and leaflet were developed but not yet distributed
<i>Website development</i>	Unique visitors: > 1500/year Unique page visits: > 3000/year No. of downloads: > 70/year	The website is being developed and will be live in October.
<i>Social Media: launch of project channels on LinkedIn and Twitter</i>	No. of posts/retweets: 1 per week; No. of impressions: > 300 per post; No. of engagements >10 per post	Impressions are below the target value on most posts because the number of followers is increasing slowly but the other two targets have been achieved.
<i>Newsletter</i>	No. of newsletters: 7 (2/year) No. of subscribers: > 100	1st issue to be launched in December 2024.
<i>Press Release</i>	No. of press releases: 8 No. of media insertions: > 25	5 press releases launched 11 media insertions
<i>Joint Events, Workshops and Networking</i>	No. of events: 5 No. of participants: > 150	0
<i>Technology Brochure</i>	No. of technical brochures: > 4	0
<i>Promotional Videos presenting project and tests carried out</i>	No. of videos: 3 No. Of views: > 300/per video	2 videos with 445 views and 767 views

<i>Training Workshops and Webinars</i>	No. of training workshops: > 3 No. of webinars: > 5 No. of participants: > 100	0
<i>Site Visits or other forms of direct demonstration of outcomes at LLS</i>	> 20 companies > 200 visitors	0
<i>Best Practices and Recommendations Manual for industry and policymakers</i>	> 3 courses > 1 handbook	0
<i>Standards, Technical Committees and Regulations contributions</i>	> 5 contributions	0
<i>Joint Meetings and clustering with other EU consortia under the umbrella of the REPowerEU initiative and other European workgroups</i>	> 10 cooperations > 3 joint meetings	0
<i>Workshops, Webinars and Open Educational Resources (OER)</i>	> 5 workshops or webinars; > 3 OER	0
<i>Publications in peer-reviewed OA scientific journals</i>	> 20 OA journal publications	0
<i>Presentations in scientific conferences</i>	> 20 presentations, reaching > 1000 academics	0
<i>EU and Industry events, Fairs and Exhibitions, including EU Innovation Days, Enlit, EUSEW, Innogrid, CIRED and IEEE T&D</i>	> 8 events, > 1000 experts	0
<i>Summer Schools, Master Classes and Seminars organisation</i>	> 3 events > 100 participants	0
<i>Replication Advisory Group establishment to monitor and foster replication beyond the consortium</i>	> 10 members from all partner countries	0
<i>EU-DREAM main outreach Final Event organisation</i>	> 50 stakeholders	0

Conclusion

The EU-DREAM project is set to play a pivotal role in transforming consumer interaction with the energy market through innovative digital solutions.

The D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan, as outlined in this report, serves as a comprehensive blueprint for ensuring the project's visibility, engagement, and impact. By detailing clear strategies, tools, and campaigns, this deliverable lays the foundation for effective communication and dissemination efforts throughout the project's lifecycle and beyond.

The continuous monitoring and updating of this plan will be crucial to adapting to the project's progress and ensuring that its objectives—enhancing consumer awareness, trust, and participation in energy transition—are fully realized. Therefore, an update of this deliverable will be provided at M14 (August 2025) and M28 (October 2026).

Ultimately, the EU-DREAM project aims to empower consumers, foster energy efficiency, and contribute to a more informed and proactive energy market across Europe.

References

(s.d.). Twitter: EU-DREAM: https://x.com/eudream_project

(s.d.). LinkedIn: EU-DREAM: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-dream/>

Appendix

Appendix 1 Project Visual Brand Identity

EU-DREAM
Brand Manual

LOGO CONSTRUCTION, CLEARSPACE AND COMPUTATION

It is important to keep corporate marks clear of any other graphic elements.

To regulate this, an exclusion zone has been established around the project mark. This exclusion zone indicates the closest any other graphic element or message can be positioned in relation to the mark.

Clearspace

DEFINITION

Whenever you use the logo, it should be surrounded with clear space to ensure its visibility and impact. No graphic elements of any kind should invade this zone.

COMPUTATION

To work out the clearspace take the height of the logo and divide it by four: (Clearspace = Height / 4).

EU-DREAM
Brand Manual

Logo Backgrounds

Logo do's and don'ts

PLEASE READ CAREFULLY THE DO'S AND DON'TS

- Do not place the logo type on 1 line
- Do not invert the logo symbol
- Do not alter the logo symbol
- Do not alter the logo type style
- Do not change the size relationship between the logo symbol and logo type.
- Never change the proportions of the logo vertically or horizontally or alter the appearance in any way

EU-DREAM
Brand Manual

PROJECT COLOR SYSTEM

DIGITAL SERVICES

ENERGY TRANSITION

Color Codes

CMYK : C100 M93 Y39 K46
 RGB : R000 G13 B076
 Web : #020d4c

Color Codes

CMYK : C36 M00 Y97 K00
 RGB : R188 G241 B036
 Web : #bc124

COMMUNITY

CONSUMERS

Color Codes

CMYK : C84 M27 Y47 K11
 RGB : R000 G128 B128
 Web : #008080

Color Codes

CMYK : C00 M61 Y90 K00
 RGB : R242 G123 B036
 Web : #f27624

EU-DREAM
Brand Manual

PROJECT TYPOGRAPHY

Primary Font :
Agenor Neue Regular

Letters

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z
a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k	l	m
n	o	p	q	r	s	t	u	v	w	x	y	z

Numbers

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
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>>

EU-DREAM

Brand Manual

Secondary Font :
Open Sans
 -

Letters

Open Sans	A B C D E F G H I J K L M
Light	N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
	a b c d e f g h i j k l m
	n o p q r s t u v w x y z

Open Sans	A B C D E F G H I J K L M
Bold	N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
	a b c d e f g h i j k l m
	n o p q r s t u v w x y z

Numbers

Open Sans	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0
Light	

Open Sans	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0
Bold	

Appendix 2 Project Scope Infographics

Appendix 3 Project Roll-up banner, poster, leaflet and flyer

EU-DREAM

BRIDGING THE DIGITAL DIVIDE IN ENERGY

EU-DREAM aims to develop next-generation energy services, solutions, and products that truly benefit consumers.

Our initiatives will be tested and demonstrated in six Living Labs:

- PORTUGAL:** AI-POWERED RENEWABLE ENERGY COMMUNITIES
- BELGIUM:** ENERGY POVERTY AND VULNERABLE CONSUMERS IMPACTS
- ITALY:** ENERGY FLEXIBILITY AT RESIDENTIAL SCALE AND INTEROPERABILITY
- IRELAND:** CONSUMERS EMPOWERMENT FOR ENERGY MANAGEMENT
- GREECE:** SMART ENERGY SERVICES FOR MULTI-ENERGY VECTORS
- DENMARK:** DT-ENABLED RESIDENTIAL ISMICOGRID

Funded by the European Union

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Discover more at eu-dream.eu

Effective Uptake of Digital services to Repower European consumers and communities as Active participants in energy transition and Markets

Bridging the Digital Divide in Energy!

CONTEXT

Almost 80% of Europeans are not engaged in the energy transition. Digital technologies are key to involve society, but consumers still struggle to keep pace.

EU-DREAM brings together leading energy industry and research partners to drive innovation in digital tools and services.

Aligned with the EU Action Plan on the Digitalisation of the Energy System, **the project aims to develop next-generation energy services, solutions, and products that truly benefit consumers.**

OBJECTIVES

- Empowering Consumers with Data-Driven Solutions
- Development of AI-based assistant tool and NLP-based intermediary
- Development of a cloud-based data-sharing platform
- Development of new AI-powered and simplified digital platforms
- Creation of User-Friendly digital tools
- Innovative Market Mechanisms
- Consumer-Centric Approaches
- Improvement of Energy Literacy

Energy management system with AI-based assistant tool and NLP-based intermediary of EU-DREAM.

These innovative tools will make energy management accessible and understandable.

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Discover more at eu-dream.eu

Contact us at info@eu-dream.eu

EU-DREAM

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Discover more at eu-dream.eu

BRIDGING THE DIGITAL DIVIDE IN ENERGY

EU-DREAM

EU-DREAM brings together leading energy industry and research partners to drive innovation in digital tools and services.

Aligned with the EU Action Plan on the Digitalisation of the Energy System, **EU-DREAM aims to develop next-generation energy services, solutions, and products that truly benefit consumers.**

The project initiatives will be tested and demonstrated in **six Living Labs** across Portugal, Belgium, Italy, Ireland, Greece, and Denmark.

The Project in a Nutshell

 6 LIVING LABS			
--	---	--	--

Key Expected Impacts

 35% CO2 EMISSIONS REDUCTION			
---	--	--	--

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x.com/eudream_project

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EU-DREAM

EU-DREAM aims to develop next-generation energy services, solutions, and products that truly benefit consumers.

Discover more at eu-dream.eu

BRIDGING THE DIGITAL DIVIDE IN ENERGY

Consortium

The EU-DREAM project (JUL 2024-DEC 2027) is composed of a consortium of 22 participants (led by the University of Porto), from 9 countries and is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program with a total of M4.5€.

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[z.com/eudream_project](https://www.z.com/eudream_project)

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About EU-DREAM project

Almost 80% of Europeans are not engaged in the energy transition. Digital technologies are key to involve society, but consumers still struggle to keep pace.

EU-DREAM brings together leading energy industry and research partners to drive innovation in digital tools and services.

Aligned with the EU Action Plan on the Digitalisation of the Energy System, the project aims to develop next-generation energy services, solutions, and products that truly benefit consumers.

EU-DREAM focus on overcoming barriers and understanding consumer motivations, combining technological advancements with Social Sciences and Humanities expertise.

The **AI-based assistant** will optimize settings based on individual preferences, while the **NLP intermediary** will facilitate seamless communication in everyday language.

Additionally, **Digital Twins** of households will be created using real-time data, enabling precise monitoring and optimization of energy use.

These innovative tools will make energy management accessible and understandable.

Living Labs

The solutions will be tested and demonstrated in six Living Labs across Portugal, Belgium, Italy, Ireland, Greece, and Denmark.

Delivering Impact: Advancing a Digital and Efficient Energy Future

Bridging the Digital Divide in Energy!

Horizon-CL5-2023-D3-03
Grant Agreement 101160614

Appendix 5 Press Releases sent in Ireland, Portugal, Greece, Belgium and Italy

Ireland:

New European Project Aims to Increase Consumers' Involvement in the Energy Market by Using AI

Dublin, Ireland 17 July, 2024 - Nearly 80% of Europeans aren't involved in the energy transition, often because they don't know how. Digital tools can make it easier for people to actively participate and support the shift to a greener future, but consumers still lack user-friendly solutions. Leading energy industry and research collaborators from across Europe are launching the EU-DREAM project this month to accelerate innovation in digital tools and enhance the adoption of digital services in the energy market.

The EU-DREAM project stands for Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets and focuses on improving consumer interaction with the energy market. It aims to simplify complex energy management processes and enhance customer awareness, trust, and confidence through the introduction of an Artificial Intelligence (AI) -based assistant and a Natural Language Processing (NLP) intermediary.

The project is led by the University of Porto (Portugal) and 16 other collaborators from nine countries. The project is set to develop next-generation energy services, solutions, and products, fully tested and demonstrated in six living labs (LLs) across six EU countries: Portugal, Belgium, Italy, Ireland, Greece, and Denmark. Each LL will be focusing on different aspects of energy innovation:

- LL1 (Coimbra, Portugal): AI-powered renewable energy communities
- LL2 (Genk, Belgium): Addressing energy poverty and impacts on vulnerable consumers
- LL3 (Northern Italy, Italy): Energy flexibility and interoperability at the residential scale
- LL4 (Dublin, Ireland): Empowering consumers for energy management
- LL5 (Thessaloniki and other cities, Greece): Smart energy services for multi-energy vectors
- LL6 (Aalborg, Denmark): DT-enabled residential IoT microgrid

“These innovative tools will translate intricate energy market details into everyday language, making energy management accessible and understandable. The AI-based assistant will act as an energy attorney for users, optimizing energy settings according to individual preferences, while the NLP intermediary will facilitate seamless communication in layman's terms,” explained João Catalão, full professor, Faculty of Engineering at the University of Porto (Portugal).

The Irish LL4, led by SSE Airtricity in collaboration with EPRI Europe and DCSix Technologies, aims to address consumers' ability to optimise energy usage in Ireland through real-time data analysis and AI algorithms, ensuring efficient usage and minimizing grid reliance. “Innovations that help with an equitable, affordable clean energy transition are key to meeting net-zero targets,” said Mário Couto, technical leader at EPRI Europe. “We are pleased to work with SSE Airtricity and DCSix Technologies on the lab, which could provide consumers with the tools needed as part of an effective energy transformation.”

Additionally, a Digital Twin (DT) of households will be created using real-time data from sensors, allowing for precise monitoring and optimization of energy use. These household DTs will integrate into broader community DTs, providing valuable insights for new market designs and consumer-oriented business models.

The project, from July 2024 to December 2027, is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program, under agreement no. 101160614.

For more information about EU-DREAM and its initiatives, please contact:

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Portugal:

Novo projeto europeu quer aumentar o envolvimento dos consumidores no mercado de energia através da Inteligência Artificial

Porto, Portugal 16 Julho, 2024 – Quase 80% dos europeus não participam na transição energética, principalmente por falta de conhecimento sobre como fazê-lo. As ferramentas digitais podem facilitar a participação ativa e suportar a transição para um futuro mais sustentável, mas alguns consumidores não têm ainda acesso a dispositivos intuitivos e de fácil utilização.

A Universidade do Porto e a Cleanwatts Digital, juntamente com 16 outras Instituições europeias líderes do setor da energia, acabam de lançar o projeto europeu EU-DREAM, para acelerar a inovação em ferramentas digitais e melhorar a adoção de serviços digitais no mercado de energia.

O projeto EU-DREAM, (Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets), pretende melhorar a interação dos consumidores com o mercado de energia, simplificando processos complexos de gestão de energia e aumentando a consciencialização, confiança e segurança do consumidor através da introdução de um assistente baseado em Inteligência Artificial (AI) e de um intermediário de Processamento de Linguagem Natural (PLN).

O EU-DREAM vai desenvolver serviços, soluções e produtos de energia da próxima geração, totalmente testados e demonstrados em seis laboratórios vivos (Living Lab – LL) em seis países da União Europeia: Portugal, Bélgica, Itália, Irlanda, Grécia e Dinamarca. Cada LL focar-se-á em diferentes aspetos da inovação energética:

- LL1 (Coimbra, Portugal): Comunidades de energia renovável em ambiente residencial urbano, com forte envolvimento dos utilizadores através de ferramentas de linguagem.

- LL2 (Genk, Bélgica): Pobreza energética e o seu impacto sobre os consumidores mais vulneráveis.
- LL3 (Norte de Itália, Itália): Flexibilidade e interoperabilidade energética em ambiente residencial.
- LL4 (Dublin, Irlanda): Capacitação de consumidores para a gestão de energia.
- LL5 (Salónica e outras cidades, Grécia): Serviços de energia inteligentes para vetores multienergéticos.
- LL6 (Aalborg, Dinamarca): Micro-rede residencial habilitada por DT (Digital Twin – Réplica Digital)

"Estas ferramentas inovadoras traduzirão pormenores complexos do mercado de energia em linguagem quotidiana, tornando a gestão de energia acessível e compreensível. O assistente baseado em IA atuará como um consultor de energia para os utilizadores, otimizando as configurações de energia de acordo com as preferências individuais, enquanto o intermediário de PLN comunicará recorrendo a linguagem mais acessível ao utilizador comum" explicou João Catalão, Professor Catedrático da Faculdade de Engenharia da Universidade do Porto (Portugal).

Além disso, será criado um Digital Twin – uma réplica digital (DT) – das residências, usando dados em tempo real de sensores, permitindo uma monitorização precisa e uma otimização do uso da energia. Esses DTs residenciais serão integrados em DTs comunitários mais amplos, fornecendo informação imprescindível para novos desenhos de mercado e modelos de negócios orientados para o consumidor.

Em Portugal, o LL será constituído por cinco comunidades de energia em Coimbra, um total de 40 residências. "O laboratório explorará novas abordagens para interagir com os utilizadores finais por meio de uma plataforma digital com soluções baseadas em voz e processamento de linguagem natural. Essas iniciativas irão melhorar as ofertas de flexibilidade e otimizar o uso de energia, promovendo uma maior adesão dos utilizadores que, ao aumentarem a utilização de formas de energia renovável, abrirão caminho a um futuro mais sustentável.", explica Jose Luis Malaquias, Especialista de Inovação da Cleanwatts, empresa que lidera a coordenação técnica do projecto e que desenvolve o LL de Coimbra.

O projeto tem a duração de 3 anos e meio – de Julho de 2024 a Dezembro de 2027 – e é financiado pelo programa Horizon Europe da Comissão Europeia, com o número 101160614.

Para mais informações sobre o EU-DREAM, por favor contacte:
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Greece:

Νέο ευρωπαϊκό έργο για την αύξηση της συμμετοχής των καταναλωτών στην αγορά ενέργειας με τη χρήση τεχνητής νοημοσύνης

Σχεδόν το 80% των Ευρωπαίων δεν συμμετέχουν στη ενεργειακή μετάβαση, συχνά επειδή δεν έχουν την τεχνογνωσία. Τα ψηφιακά εργαλεία μπορούν να διευκολύνουν τους πολίτες να συμμετέχουν ενεργά και να υποστηρίξουν τη μετάβαση σε ένα πιο βιώσιμο μέλλον αλλά εξακολουθούν να στερούνται φιλικών προς το χρήστη λύσεων. Κορυφαίοι συνεργάτες της βιομηχανίας της ενέργειας και της έρευνας από όλη την Ευρώπη εγκαινιάζουν αυτόν τον μήνα το έργο EU-DREAM για να επιταχύνουν την καινοτομία στα ψηφιακά εργαλεία και να ενισχύσουν την υιοθέτηση ψηφιακών υπηρεσιών στην αγορά ενέργειας.

Το έργο EU-DREAM, που σημαίνει Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets, στοχεύει στη βελτίωση της αλληλεπίδρασης των καταναλωτών με την αγορά ενέργειας, απλοποιώντας πολύπλοκες διαδικασίες διαχείρισης ενέργειας και αυξάνοντας την ευαισθητοποίηση, την εμπιστοσύνη και την ασφάλεια των καταναλωτών μέσω της εισαγωγής ενός βοηθού βασισμένου στην Τεχνητή Νοημοσύνη (AI) και ενός διαμεσολαβητή βασισμένου στο Natural Language Processing (NLP).

Σύμφωνα με σχετική ανακοίνωση, το έργο ηγείται από το Πανεπιστήμιο του Πόρτο (Πορτογαλία) και από άλλους 16 συνεργάτες από εννέα χώρες. Το έργο στοχεύει στην ανάπτυξη υπηρεσιών, λύσεων και προϊόντων επόμενης γενιάς στον τομέα της ενέργειας, τα οποία θα δοκιμαστούν και θα παρουσιαστούν σε έξι εργαστήρια ζωντανής εφαρμογής (Living Labs - LLs) σε έξι χώρες της ΕΕ: την Πορτογαλία, το Βέλγιο, την Ιταλία, την Ιρλανδία, την Ελλάδα και τη Δανία. Κάθε Living Lab θα επικεντρωθεί σε διαφορετικές πτυχές της ενεργειακής καινοτομίας:

- LL1 (Κοΐμπρα, Πορτογαλία): Κοινότητες ανανεώσιμης ενέργειας με εφαρμογές Τεχνητής Νοημοσύνης (AI).
- LL2 (Γκενκ, Βέλγιο): Αντιμετώπιση της ενεργειακής φτώχειας και των επιπτώσεων στους ευάλωτους καταναλωτές.
- LL3 (Βόρεια Ιταλία, Ιταλία): Ενεργειακή ευελιξία και διαλειτουργικότητα σε οικιστικό περιβάλλον.
- LL4 (Δουβλίνο, Ιρλανδία): Κινητοποίηση των καταναλωτών για την διαχείριση της ενέργειας.
- LL5 (Θεσσαλονίκη και άλλες πόλεις, Ελλάδα): Έξυπνες ενεργειακές υπηρεσίες για πολυενεργειακούς φορείς
- LL6 (Άλμποργκ, Δανία): Οικιακά IoT μικροδίκτυα με δυνατότητες DT (Digital Twin - Ψηφιακό Δίδυμο).

"Αυτά τα καινοτόμα εργαλεία θα μεταφράσουν τις περίπλοκες λεπτομέρειες της αγοράς ενέργειας σε καθημερινή γλώσσα, καθιστώντας τη διαχείριση της ενέργειας προσιτή και κατανοητή. Ο βοηθός βασισμένος σε τεχνητή νοημοσύνη θα λειτουργεί ως σύμβουλος ενέργειας για τους χρήστες, βελτιστοποιώντας τις ρυθμίσεις ενέργειας ανάλογα με τις ατομικές προτιμήσεις, ενώ ο διαμεσολαβητής NLP θα διευκολύνει την επικοινωνία χρησιμοποιώντας μια πιο προσιτή γλώσσα προς το κοινό," εξήγησε ο João Catalão, καθηγητής στη Σχολή Μηχανικών του Πανεπιστημίου του Πόρτο (Πορτογαλία). Στο πλαίσιο του Ελληνικού Living Lab θα συμμετέχουν 100 οικιακοί καταναλωτές ηλεκτρικής ενέργειας και φυσικού αερίου, οι οποίοι θα έχουν τη δυνατότητα παρακολούθησης και ελέγχου της κατανάλωσης τους, μέσω της χρήσης συσκευών IoT της Ελληνικής startup εταιρείας domx. Επιπλέον θα αποκτήσουν πρόσβαση σε μία εύχρηστη εφαρμογή κινητού τηλεφώνου που θα επιτρέπει την απεικόνιση των διαφόρων ενεργειακών ροών και την αλληλεπίδραση με κτιριακά συστήματα σε πραγματικό χρόνο, εστιάζοντας στη βελτίωση της εμπειρίας χρήσης από άπειρους χρήστες που συνήθως επιβαρύνονται σημαντικά από την πολυπλοκότητα χρήσης νέων ψηφιακών τεχνολογιών και συστημάτων.

Επιπλέον, θα δημιουργηθεί ένα Ψηφιακό Δίδυμο (DT) για τα νοικοκυριά χρησιμοποιώντας δεδομένα πραγματικού χρόνου από αισθητήρες, επιτρέποντας την ακριβή παρακολούθηση και βελτιστοποίηση της χρήσης ενέργειας. Αυτά τα Ψηφιακά Δίδυμα νοικοκυριά θα ενσωματωθούν σε ευρύτερα Ψηφιακά

Δίδυμα κοινοτήτων, προσφέροντας πολύτιμες πληροφορίες για τον νέο σχεδιασμό των αγορών και για επιχειρηματικά μοντέλα προσαρμοσμένα στον καταναλωτή.

Το έργο, το οποίο διαρκεί 3,5 χρόνια από τον Ιούλιο του 2024 έως τον Δεκέμβριο του 2027, χρηματοδοτείται από το πρόγραμμα Horizon Europe της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης, στο πλαίσιο της συμφωνίας με αριθ. 101160614.

Για περισσότερες πληροφορίες για το έργο EU-DREAM παρακαλώ επικοινωνήστε με τους υπεύθυνους από την Ελληνική πλευρά:

Παντελής Μπίσκας, Καθηγητής

Τμήμα Ηλεκτρολόγων Μηχανικών και Μηχανικών Υπολογιστών ΑΠΘ

Τηλέφωνα: 2310-994352, 6973-841753

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domx IoT Technologies

Τηλέφωνα: 2313-252420, 6975-260268

Belgium :

EU-Dream project aims to increase consumers' involvement in the energy market by using AI

Mon 22/07/2024

Mol, Belgium, 18 July 2024 – Nearly 80% of Europeans aren't actively involved in the energy transition, often because they don't know how. While digital tools can facilitate active participation and support the shift to a greener future, consumers still lack user-friendly solutions. Leading energy industry and research collaborators from across Europe, including VITO/EnergyVille, are launching the EU-DREAM project this month to accelerate innovation in digital tools and enhance the adoption of digital services in the energy market.

Led by the University of Porto (Portugal) and 16 collaborators from nine countries, the EU-DREAM project (Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets) aims to transform consumer interaction with the energy market. The project seeks to simplify complex energy management processes and boost customer awareness, trust, and confidence through the introduction of an Artificial Intelligence (AI) -based assistant and a Natural Language Processing (NLP) intermediary.

Complex details into everyday language

"These innovative tools will translate complex energy market details into everyday language, making energy management accessible and understandable," explained João Catalão, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto.

The EU-DREAM project will develop and test next-generation energy services, solutions, and products in six living labs across Europe, each focusing on different aspects of energy innovation. One such lab is the Open Thor Living Lab, where VITO/EnergyVille will identify, together with the living lab participants, what is the interest of vulnerable consumers in adopting EU-DREAM innovative tools. Equipped with rooftop building-integrated PV, solar thermal collectors, heat pumps, thermal and electrical storage, and home batteries, Open Thor exemplifies a holistic approach to sustainable energy solutions. The lab aims to empower

vulnerable communities through innovative digital tools, enhancing energy literacy, and promoting economic resilience.

Empower vulnerable customers

"The Open Thor Living Lab is pivotal in our mission to empower vulnerable consumers through innovative digital solutions," said Luciana Marques, Senior Researcher at VITO/EnergyVille. "We aim to create tangible impacts that improve lives and contribute to a more sustainable future by developing tools helping consumers to engage in energy markets. With EU-DREAM tools, any end-consumer, who may or may not understand these complex markets rules, will be able to better manage their demand and support the energy transition while gaining extra revenues from it."

VITO/EnergyVille is also playing a critical role in leading the work package on market design for digital tools update and flexibility services, ensuring the project's innovations align with market needs and regulatory frameworks.

The full list of partners include:

Universidade do Porto and Cleanwatts Digital SA (Portugal); EPRI Europe, SSE Airtricity LTD and DCSix Technologies Limited (Ireland); Aalborg Universitet (Denmark); Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY (Finland); AKKA High Tech – Akkodis Group (France); Universidad de Castilla - La Mancha (Spain); Agenzia Nazionale per le Nuove Tecnologie, L'energia e lo Sviluppo Economico Sostenibile, Consorzio Interuniversitario Nazionale per Energia e Sistemi Elettrici, Fondazione Links - Leading Innovation & Knowledge for Society, IREN SPA and IREN Mercato SPA (Italy); Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis and DOMX Idiotiki Kefalaiouchiki Etaireia (Greece); Vlaamse Instelling Voor Technologisch Onderzoek N.V. (Belgium).

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Italy:

Un nuovo progetto europeo mira ad aumentare il coinvolgimento dei consumatori nel mercato energetico utilizzando l'intelligenza artificiale

Dublino, Irlanda, 17 luglio 2024 - Quasi l'80% degli europei non è coinvolto nella transizione energetica, spesso perché non sa come fare. Gli strumenti digitali possono semplificare la partecipazione attiva delle persone e il supporto al passaggio a un futuro più verde, ma i consumatori non hanno ancora soluzioni user-friendly. I principali collaboratori del settore energetico e della ricerca di tutta Europa stanno lanciando questo mese il progetto EU-DREAM per accelerare l'innovazione negli strumenti digitali e migliorare l'adozione di servizi digitali nel mercato energetico.

L'acronimo del progetto EU-DREAM significa Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets (Adozione efficace dei servizi digitali per rilanciare i consumatori e le comunità europee come partecipanti attivi nella transizione energetica e nei mercati). Il progetto si concentra sul miglioramento dell'interazione dei consumatori con il mercato energetico. Mira a semplificare i complessi processi di gestione dell'energia e ad aumentare la consapevolezza, la fiducia e la sicurezza dei clienti attraverso l'introduzione di un assistente basato sull'intelligenza artificiale (AI) e di un intermediario di elaborazione del linguaggio naturale (NLP).

Il progetto è guidato dall'Università di Porto (Portogallo) con 16 partecipanti di nove Paesi. Il progetto è destinato a sviluppare servizi, soluzioni e prodotti energetici di prossima generazione, completamente validati e dimostrati in sei laboratori "living lab" (LL) in sei Paesi dell'UE: Portogallo, Belgio, Italia, Irlanda, Grecia e Danimarca. Ogni LL si concentrerà su diversi aspetti dell'innovazione energetica:

- LL1 (Coimbra, Portugal): Gestire le comunità di energia rinnovabile alimentate dall'intelligenza artificiale
- LL2 (Genk, Belgium): Affrontare la povertà energetica e gli impatti sui consumatori vulnerabili
- LL3 (Northern Italy, Italy): Flessibilità energetica e interoperabilità su scala residenziale
- LL4 (Dublin, Ireland): Dare potere ai consumatori per la gestione dell'energia
- LL5 (Thessaloniki and other cities, Greece): Servizi energetici intelligenti per vettori multi-energia
- LL6 (Aalborg, Denmark): Microrete IoT residenziale abilitata DT (Digital Twin, Gemello Digitale)

"Questi strumenti innovativi tradurranno i dettagli complessi del mercato energetico in un linguaggio quotidiano, rendendo la gestione energetica accessibile e comprensibile. L'assistente basato sull'intelligenza artificiale fungerà da consulente energetico per gli utenti, ottimizzando le impostazioni energetiche in base alle preferenze individuali, mentre l'intermediario NLP faciliterà una comunicazione fluida in termini semplici", ha spiegato João Catalão, professore ordinario presso la Facoltà di Ingegneria dell'Università di Porto (Portogallo).

Il LL4 irlandese, guidato da SSE Airtricity in collaborazione con EPRI Europe e DCSix Technologies, intende affrontare la capacità dei consumatori di ottimizzare l'uso dell'energia in Irlanda attraverso analisi dei dati in tempo reale e algoritmi di intelligenza artificiale, garantendo un uso efficiente e riducendo al minimo la dipendenza dalla rete. "Le innovazioni che aiutano con una transizione equa e conveniente all'energia pulita sono fondamentali per raggiungere gli obiettivi net-zero", ha affermato Mário Couto, responsabile tecnico di EPRI Europe. "Siamo lieti di lavorare con SSE Airtricity e DCSix Technologies in laboratorio, che potrebbe fornire ai consumatori gli strumenti necessari come parte di un'efficace trasformazione energetica". Inoltre, verrà creato un Digital Twin (DT) delle famiglie utilizzando dati in tempo reale dai sensori, consentendo un monitoraggio e un'ottimizzazione precisi dell'uso dell'energia. Questi DT delle famiglie si integreranno in DT della comunità più ampi, fornendo preziose informazioni per nuovi progetti di mercato e modelli aziendali orientati al consumatore.

Il progetto, attivo da luglio 2024 a dicembre 2027, è finanziato dal programma Horizon Europe dell'Unione Europea, con l'accordo no. 101160614.

Per ulteriori informazioni sul progetto EU-DREAM e sulle sue iniziative, il riferimento è il Contact Information indicato nel seguito.

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